

Green and highly selective protocol for the synthesis of oximes

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Abstract : A green and efficient protocol has been developed for the synthesis of either exclusively a monoxime or exclusively a dioxime from a host of 1,2-dicarbonyl compounds on silica.

Keywords : Oxime synthesis, dicarbonyls, aldehydes, ketones, silica.

Introduction

Monoxime and dioxime are considered as a versatile important organic precursor for the synthesis of heterocycle viz. quinoxaline¹, imidazole², oxadiazole³, oxazole⁴, oxazoline⁵ etc. as well as for functional group transformations⁶⁻¹³. Such a huge application of oximes and also the associated drawback of traditional method of its preparation such as no selectivity, use of hazardous chemicals, high cost, poor chemical yields, requirements of long reaction time and tedious work-up procedures, has limit their use under the aspect of chemical selectivity as well as environmentally benign process. Reports are still scanty towards the development of a simple, selective and greener protocol for the preparation of such an important class of derivatives. Although, Vukićević *et al.*¹⁴ has reported the synthesis of oxime on solid support and Hajipour *et al.*¹⁵ has reported simple procedure for oxime synthesis, but in both the cases, use of strong base has limit their application as a green and selective protocol. Attempted oximation in the absence of base was not encouraging due to longer reaction time and comparatively low yield^{16,17}. It was therefore felt necessary to develop selective, easy, safe and green procedure for oxime synthesis. In view of the above and in continuation our studies towards the development of greener methodology for organic transformation¹⁸, we report herein a very simple, highly selective and green protocol for oxime preparation from carbonyl compounds. The beauty of the protocol has been its selectivity that can be applied either for exclusively monoxime or dioxime preparation from sym-

metrical-1,2-dicarbonyl system or from 1,2-unsymmetrical dicarbonyl systems by regioselective pathway.

After getting satisfactory results from a model study by a host of 1,2-dicarbonyls with hydroxyl amine on solid support, the process was optimized and subsequently applied on a host of 1,2-dicarbonyls with an excellent selectivity and yield of the products (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Selective synthesis of mono and dioxime from 1,2-dicarbonyl system.

Results and discussion

To cope up with the growing demand towards the development of greener protocols for organic transformation, our laboratory has devoted a significant effort to develop efficient protocols for the preparation of a diverse collection of organic derivatives from common intermediates following simple and greener methodologies. The present investigation has developed a clean and selective method for the synthesis of oxime derivatives from a wide variety of carbonyl compounds.

A model study with benzil on silica - NH₂OH.HCl at room temperature (*vide infra*) gave an excellent yield of the monoxime and at elevated temperature gave excellent yield of dioxime. Since no selective protocol is being reported so far either for exclusive formation of monoxime or dioxime from a 1,2-dicarbonyl compounds, a change

in reaction temperature and in the molar proportion of the reactants (Table 1) induces selectivity in the protocol towards monoxime and/or dioxime formation from 1,2-dicarbonyl system. For example, benzil and hydroxyl amine hydrochloride in the mol ratio of 1 : 1.2 afforded only the monoxime (97%), at room temperature and 1 : 2.2 mol ratio of the same combination yielded exclusively the dioxime at 50 °C (entries 1–2, Table 1). Similar result was also obtained with phenyl glyoxal (entries 3–4, Table 1) as a dicarbonyl compounds. Among the two different carbonyl groups in phenyl glyoxal only aldehyde function takes part in the formation of monoxime following regioselective pathway.

Table 1. Selective synthesis of mono and dioxime from 1,2-dicarbonyl system

Entry	R1	R2	Mol ratio ^a	Temp.	Time (h)	Yield ^b	
						Monoxime	Dioxime
1	Ph	Ph	1 : 1.20	r.t	6	97%	Nil
2	Ph	Ph	1 : 2.20	50 °C	5	Nil	95%
3	H	Ph	1 : 1.20	r.t	3	97%	nil
4	H	Ph	1 : 2.20	50 °C	4.5	Nil	96

^aMol ratio of 1,2-dicarbonyl and hydroxyl amine.

^bIsolated yield.

Several experiments were then carried out with a wide variety of aromatic monocarbonyl compounds to explore the potential of the newly developed method as a general protocol for synthesis of oximes (Table 2). In deciding the best reaction condition for the above transformation, aromatic aldehydes having electron withdrawing (entries 1–4, Table 2) as well as electron donating group (entries 5–10, Table 2) were tried in comparison to the unsubstituted substrate (entry 11, Table 2) in the above protocol and the transformation was found independent on the nature of substituent (Scheme 2). The study also indicated that aromatic carbonyl compounds with elec-

Scheme 2. Synthesis of oxime from aromatic monocarbonyl system.

Table 2. Synthesis of oxime from aromatic monocarbonyl system

Entry	R1	R2	R3	R4	Time (h)	Temp.	%Yield ^b
1	H	NO ₂	H	H	1.5	r.t	94
						50 °C	96
2	H	H	NO ₂	H	3	r.t	91
						50 °C	97
3	H	H	H	NO ₂	1.5	r.t	95
						50 °C	98
4	H	H	H	F	4	r.t	94
						50 °C	98
5	H	OH	H	H	5	r.t	90
						50 °C	92
6	H	H	H	OH	5	r.t	91
						50 °C	92
7	H	OH	OMe	H	6.5	r.t	18
						50 °C	86
8	H	H	OMe	OH	6	r.t	24
						50 °C	89
9	H	H	OMe	H	4	r.t	91
						50 °C	94
10	H	H	H	NMe ₂	5	r.t	28
						50 °C	84
11	H	H	H	H	5	r.t	92
						50 °C	93
12	Me	H	H	H	4.5	r.t	Nil ^d
						50 °C	97
13	Ph	H	H	H	2.5	r.t	Nil ^e
						50 °C	96

^{d,e}Acyclic aromatic ketones does not react at room temperature.

tron withdrawing substituents mostly at *ortho*- or *para*-position gave best results at room temperature and those having electron releasing substituents needed a higher temperature (50 °C) to yield the maximum product (entries 7, 8, 10, 12, 13, Table 2).

In order to establish the general applicability, we applied this present procedure on aliphatic carbonyl compounds, cyclohexanone (entry 1, Table 3). Although yields are comparatively less, large molecules like triterpenoid and steroidal ketone also showed identical results (entries 5–6, Table 3).

However, 1,3- and 1,4-dicarbonyl does not show the selectivity rather they only form the dioxime with 62–72% yield at room temperature and above 90% at 50 °C.

Table 3. Oxime of aliphatic, alicyclic, steroid and triterpenoid carbonyl system

Entry	Carbonyls	Temp.	Time (h)	% Yield ^b	
				Monoxime	Dioxime
1	Cyclohexanone	r.t	3	95	Nil
		50 °C	4	97	
2	Cyclohexa-1,2-dione	r.t	3	Nil	72
		50 °C	3	Nil	94
3	Dimedone	r.t	3	Nil	62
		50 °C	4	Nil	91
4	1,4-Butadione	r.t	4	Nil	64
		50 °C	4	Nil	90
5	Friedelin	r.t	4	68	Nil
		50 °C	4	88	
6	16-DPA	r.t	8	18	Nil
		50 °C	6	42	

Reaction procedure :

2 g/mmol silica gel (60–120 mesh) was taken on motor, mixed finely with carbonyl compound, add 1.2 mmol of hydroxylamine hydrochloride for monoxime and 2.2 mmol for dioxime and then mixed thoroughly with pestle. The reaction mixture was then allowed to stir at room temperature or at 50 °C as the case may be on a magnetic stirrer using oil bath. The completion of reaction was monitored by TLC. The product was extracted with ether, washed with water (30 ml × 3), dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and purified by column chromatography using neutral active alumina.

Experimental

IR spectra were recorded in KBr on Shimadzu FT-IR 8300 spectrometer, ¹H and ¹³C NMR were recorded on 300 MHz Bruker Avance FT-NMR spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

Conclusion :

In conclusion we have developed a highly selective, green, mild and highly efficient protocol for the synthesis of oxime from 1,2-dicarbonyl and wide varieties of aldehydes and ketones.

Spectroscopic data of some representative compounds :**Benzophenone oxime (Table 2, entry 13) :**

IR(KBr) : 3214, 1557, 1377 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 7.08–7.13 (1H, m), 7.32–7.38 (2H, m), 7.50–7.62 (3H, m), 7.77–7.80 (2H, m), 7.94–7.97

(2H, m), 10.26 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 120.8, 124.1, 128.1, 128.8, 129.0, 132.0, 135.4, 139.6, 166.0.

Benzil monoxime (Table 1, entry 1) :

IR (KBr) : 3238, 1674, 1593 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.24–7.64 (8H, m), 7.96–7.99 (2H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 126.4, 128.2, 128.4, 128.9, 129.1, 129.4, 130.3, 130.5, 130.9, 134.6, 157.1, 194.2.

Benzil dioxime (Table 1, entry 2) :

IR (KBr) : 3180, 1649, 1498 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 7.36–7.38 (6H, m), 7.48–7.49 (4H, m), 11.49 (2H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 125.9, 129.1, 129.7, 133.2, 151.1.

Phenylglyoxal monoxime (Table 1, entry 3) :

IR (KBr) : 3419, 1701, 1651, 1598 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 7.49–7.54 (1H, m), 7.61–7.67 (1H, m), 7.14–7.98 (2H, m), 8.03 (1H, s), 12.70 (1H, s); ¹H NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 128.8, 130.0, 133.6, 136.5, 148.2, 189.5.

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